

Farmers Questionnaires

ACQUAOUNT

Jordan

Investigator name: Dr. Naem Mazahreh & Eng. Ahmad Al-Alwan

1. Farmer Name: Mahmoud Al Rajibi

Crop: Citrus

PRESENT STATUS:

1. Water use per hectare/per annum (m³ or analogous)? 7500 m³
2. Energy use (for pumping water) per annum (Kw/h or analogous)? 1100 Kilowatt
3. Average annualized price payed for energy (\$/Kw/h or analogous)? 330 US\$
4. Labour force per cultivated area hectare per annum (hours worked or analogous). This should include as many activities as possible needed for farming, including maintenance costs? 30 days
5. Average cost of labor? 750 US\$
6. Fertilizers use per hectare per annum (kg used & cost per kg)? 600 kg with total cost 840 US\$
7. Pesticides use per hectare per annum (litter used & cost per litter)? 12 litter with total cost 240 US\$
8. Cost of machine work for 1 ha? 320 US\$
9. Yield per hectare per annum (sold kg and US\$/kg)? 10 Ton Total Revenue 5600 US\$

Now suppose you can have an annual 20% improvement in saving excess water

10. Water use per hectare/per annum (m³ or analogous)? 6500 m³
11. Energy use (for pumping water) per annum (Kw/h or analogous)? 1000 Kilowatt with total cost 300 US\$
12. Labor force per cultivated area hectare per annum (hours worked or analogous). This should include as many activities as possible needed for farming, including maintenance costs? 20 days
13. Average cost of labor? 500 US\$
14. Fertilizers use per hectare per annum (kg used & cost per kg)? 520 kg with total cost 728 US\$
15. Pesticides use per hectare per annum (litter used & cost per litter)? 12 litter with total cost 240 US\$
16. Cost of machine work for 1 ha? 320 US\$
17. Yield per hectare per annum (sold kg and US\$/kg)? 10 Ton Total Revenue 5600 US\$

2. Farmer Name: Faisal Niemat

Crop: Citrus

PRESENT STATUS:

1. Water use per hectare/per annum (m³ or analogous)? 7800 m³
2. Energy use (for pumping water) per annum (Kw/h or analogous)? 1200 Kilowatt
3. Average annualized price payed for energy (\$/Kw/h or analogous): 360 US\$
4. Labour force per cultivated area hectare per annum (hours worked or analogous). This should include as many activities as possible needed for farming, including maintenance costs? 35 days
5. Average cost of labor? 875 US\$
6. Fertilizers use per hectare per annum (kg used & cost per kg)? 700 kg with total cost 980 US\$
7. Pesticides use per hectare per annum (litter used & cost per litter)? 15 litter with total cost 300 US\$
8. Cost of machine work for 1 ha? 360 US\$
9. Yield per hectare per annum (sold kg and US\$/kg)? 12 Ton Total Revenue 7000 US\$

Now suppose you can have an annual 20% improvement in saving excess water

10. Water use per hectare/per annum (m³ or analogous)? 6800 m³
11. Energy use (for pumping water) per annum (Kw/h or analogous)? 1000 Kilowatt with total cost 300 US\$
12. Labor force per cultivated area hectare per annum (hours worked or analogous). This should include as many activities as possible needed for farming, including maintenance costs? 15 days
13. Average cost of labor? 375 US\$
14. Fertilizers use per hectare per annum (kg used & cost per kg)? 600 kg with total cost 840 US\$
15. Pesticides use per hectare per annum (Litter used & cost per litter)? 15 litter with total cost 300 US\$
16. Cost of machine work for 1 ha? 360 US\$
17. Yield per hectare per annum (sold kg and US\$/kg)? 12 Ton Total Revenue 7000 US\$

3. **Farmer Name: Ishaq Sawalheh**

Crop: **Onion**

PRESENT STATUS:

1. Water use per hectare/per annum (m³ or analogous)? **5500 m³**
2. Energy use (for pumping water) per annum (Kw/h or analogous)? **800 Kilowatt**
3. Average annualized price payed for energy (\$/Kw/h or analogous): **240 US\$**
4. Labour force per cultivated area hectare per annum (hours worked or analogous). This should include as many activities as possible needed for farming, including maintenance costs? **50 days**
5. Average cost of labor? **1250 US\$**
6. Fertilizers use per hectare per annum (kg used & cost per kg)? **400 kg with total cost 560 US\$**
7. Pesticides use per hectare per annum (litter used & cost per litter)? **12 litter with total cost 168 US\$**
8. Cost of machine work for 1 ha? **350 US\$**
9. Yield per hectare per annum (sold kg and US\$/kg)? **25 Ton Total Revenue 10000 US\$**

Now suppose you can have an annual 20% improvement in saving excess water

10. Water use per hectare/per annum (m³ or analogous)? **4800 m³**
11. Energy use (for pumping water) per annum (Kw/h or analogous)? **650 Kilowatt with total cost 210 US\$**
12. Labor force per cultivated area hectare per annum (hours worked or analogous). This should include as many activities as possible needed for farming, including maintenance costs? **35 days**
13. Average cost of labor? **875 US\$**
14. Fertilizers use per hectare per annum (kg used & cost per kg)? **320 kg with total cost 450 US\$**
15. Pesticides use per hectare per annum (litter used & cost per litter)? **12 litter with total cost 168 US\$**
16. Cost of machine work for 1 ha? **350 US\$**
17. Yield per hectare per annum (sold kg and US\$/kg)? **25 Ton Total Revenue 10000 US\$**

4. Farmer Name: Atef Al Adi

Crop: Onion

PRESENT STATUS:

1. Water use per hectare/per annum (m³ or analogous)? **6000 m³**
2. Energy use (for pumping water) per annum (Kw/h or analogous)? **1000 Kilowatt**
3. Average annualized price payed for energy (\$/Kw/h or analogous): **300 US\$**
4. Labour force per cultivated area hectare per annum (hours worked or analogous). This should include as many activities as possible needed for farming, including maintenance costs? **55 days**
5. Average cost of labor? **1375 US\$**
6. Fertilizers use per hectare per annum (kg used & cost per kg)? **450 kg with total cost 630 US\$**
7. Pesticides use per hectare per annum (litter used & cost per litter)? **10 litter with total cost 150 US\$**
8. Cost of machine work for 1 ha? **380 US\$**
9. Yield per hectare per annum (sold kg and US\$/kg)? **28 Ton Total Revenue 11200 US\$**

Now suppose you can have an annual 20% improvement in saving excess water

10. Water use per hectare/per annum (m³ or analogous)? **4800 m³**
11. Energy use (for pumping water) per annum (Kw/h or analogous)? **650 Kilowatt with total cost 210 US\$**
12. Labor force per cultivated area hectare per annum (hours worked or analogous). This should include as many activities as possible needed for farming, including maintenance costs? **35 days**
13. Average cost of labor? **875 US\$**
14. Fertilizers use per hectare per annum (kg used & cost per kg)? **320 kg with total cost 450 US\$**
15. Pesticides use per hectare per annum (litter used & cost per litter)? **10 litter with total cost 150 US\$**
16. Cost of machine work for 1 ha? **380 US\$**
17. Yield per hectare per annum (sold kg and US\$/kg)? **28 Ton Total Revenue 11200 US\$**

5. **Farmer Name: Ibrahim Al Shareef**

Crop: **Potato**

PRESENT STATUS:

1. Water use per hectare/per annum (m³ or analogous)? **4300 m³**
2. Energy use (for pumping water) per annum (Kw/h or analogous)? **650 Kilowatt**
3. Average annualized price payed for energy (\$/Kw/h or analogous): **210 US\$**
4. Labour force per cultivated area hectare per annum (hours worked or analogous). This should include as many activities as possible needed for farming, including maintenance costs? **36 days**
5. Average cost of labor? **900 US\$**
6. Fertilizers use per hectare per annum (kg used & cost per kg)? **240 kg with total cost 336 US\$**
7. Pesticides use per hectare per annum (litter used & cost per litter)? **10 litter with total cost 140 US\$**
8. Cost of machine work for 1 ha? **220 US\$**
9. Yield per hectare per annum (sold kg and US\$/kg)? **30 Ton Total Revenue 8400 US\$**

Now suppose you can have an annual 20% improvement in saving excess water

10. Water use per hectare/per annum (m³ or analogous)? **4100 m³**
11. Energy use (for pumping water) per annum (Kw/h or analogous)? **600 Kilowatt with total cost 180 US\$**
12. Labor force per cultivated area hectare per annum (hours worked or analogous). This should include as many activities as possible needed for farming, including maintenance costs? **30 days**
13. Average cost of labor? **750 US\$**
14. Fertilizers use per hectare per annum (kg used & cost per kg)? **200 kg with total cost 280 US\$**
15. Pesticides use per hectare per annum (litter used & cost per litter)? **10 litter with total cost 140 US\$**
16. Cost of machine work for 1 ha? **220 US\$**
17. Yield per hectare per annum (sold kg and US\$/kg)? **30 Ton Total Revenue 8400 US\$ \$**

6. **Farmer Name: Khaleel Al- Adwan**

Crop: Eggplant

PRESENT STATUS:

1. Water use per hectare/per annum (m³ or analogous)? **5200 m³**
2. Energy use (for pumping water) per annum (Kw/h or analogous)? **700 Kilowatt**
3. Average annualized price payed for energy (\$/Kw/h or analogous): **210 US\$**
4. Labour force per cultivated area hectare per annum (hours worked or analogous). This should include as many activities as possible needed for farming, including maintenance costs? **40 days**
5. Average cost of labor? **1000 US\$**
6. Fertilizers use per hectare per annum (kg used & cost per kg)? **250 kg with total cost 350 US\$**
7. Pesticides use per hectare per annum (litter used & cost per litter)? **12 litter with total cost 252 US\$**
8. Cost of machine work for 1 ha? **180 US\$**
9. Yield per hectare per annum (sold kg and US\$/kg)? **Ton 30 Total Revenue 6300 US\$**

Now suppose you can have an annual 20% improvement in saving excess water

10. Water use per hectare/per annum (m³ or analogous)? **4700 m³**
11. Energy use (for pumping water) per annum (Kw/h or analogous)? **650 Kilowatt with total cost 210 US\$**
12. Labor force per cultivated area hectare per annum (hours worked or analogous). This should include as many activities as possible needed for farming, including maintenance costs? **32 days**
13. Average cost of labor? **800 US\$**
14. Fertilizers use per hectare per annum (kg used & cost per kg)? **200 kg with total cost 280 US\$**
15. Pesticides use per hectare per annum (litter used & cost per litter)? **12 litter with total cost 252 US\$**
16. Cost of machine work for 1 ha? **180 US\$**
17. Yield per hectare per annum (sold kg and US\$/kg)? **Ton 30 Total Revenue 6300 US\$**

ACQUAOUNT

Name	Majed alkhraisat	Country	jordan
Organization name	Jordan vally authority	Contact email	Majed.resat@mwi.gov.jo
Date	24/5/2023		

Fill the questionnaire so a Cost-Benefit Analysis can be developed. **Use approximations and annual averages** to fill the information. Fill the questionnaire **indicating data for last year and the present year**, if available.

PRESENT STATUS

1. Based on your experience in the period 2017-2021, indicate with an X when your dry period is

Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
					X	X	X	X			

2. What happens in the dry period in terms of water availability?

Indicate it in the following way, using this example:

A: Rationing water for agriculture

B: Reduce the planted area

C: stop planting the high water consumption summer crops

3. Indicate how many times you should use the actions identified in question 2 in the period 2017-2021.

For instance, if action A is done 3 times during June, write 3A in June

If action A is done 2 times and action B is done 3 times during July, write 2A+3B in July

Example:

	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
2017					2 A	3 A +2 B	5 A + 6 B+ 2 C	5 A + 8 B+ 5 C	7 A + 5 B+ 7 C	2 A +4 B +1 C		
2018												
2019												
2020												
2021												

Now fill the table for your case, using the instructions provided:

	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
2017						ABC	ABC	ABC	ABC			
2018						ABC	ABC	ABC	ABC			
2019						ABC	ABC	ABC	ABC			
2020						ABC	ABC	ABC	ABC			
2021						ABC	ABC	ABC	ABC			

4. For each action identified in question 2; what is the associated cost (for the manager) for each type of event?

Example:

Action	Costs	Costs per episode
A: Stop water supply for energy production	Increased repair costs	XX euro
B: action 2	XXX	XX euro

Please provide as much explanation of the costs as needed. Now fill the table for your case (add rows if needed):

Action	Costs	Costs per episode (JOD)
A	Operation & maintenance cost	36000
B	Operation & maintenance cost	36800
C	Operation & maintenance cost	38000